

An Essay on Making Globalization Fair: The ILO Way

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ABSTRACT

Globalization is a process of interconnectedness and liberalization in trade and commerce in the world; flow of information, technology and resources also happens with it. It has its impact, on positives and on some negatives. Growing calls for a fair globalization talks of more inclusion, rights and equality. This essay highlights the role of International Labour Organization (ILO) and its various declarations, especially Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalization for a fairer and sustainable globalization, where demands of each section is met and for a shared prosperous future.

Keywords-- ILO, Fair Globalization, Social Security, Labour

I. INTRODUCTION

Fair Globalization calls for inclusivity and more rights and entitlements, the gains of trade should work not just for corporations, but for an average worker and working class as a whole. Equality of opportunity and economic justice should be for all in our world.

"We need more investment, more political action, more priority for a fair globalization", said UN Secretary-General António Guterres, while talking about the first-ever Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Summit, on 24-25 September 2019 at New York headquarters.

The Labour 20 – L20 – representing the interests of workers at the G20 level is convened by the International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC) also had called for Commitment to Fair Globalization.

A Speech by President Barroso at the European Forum Alpbach: *"European ideas for fair globalization"* said: *At a point when new ideas are needed to make*

globalization fairer and more inclusive, and to enable people to reap its benefits, we need to see if our basic outlook on international politics, and our own role in it, passes the test of our fast-changing times.

II. GLOBALIZATION PROCESS

The globalization process over the years has produced winners and losers; it has been supported by international institutions and seen as the logical way ahead by many governments. It talks of more interconnectedness of trade, commerce and markets with reduced tariffs and also opening up of restrictions. One may argue as it may have less competition, when one talks of alternative policies. But, it is clear local markets needs protection, so does local jobs, while one also needs to check growing inequalities with fair policies. This essay is based on ILO Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalization adopted by the International Labour Conference at its Ninety-seventh Session, Geneva, 10 June 2008. Fairness is said to be related to the concept of justice, which means equality and rights of opportunity and growth. Globalization pursued passionately by the advent world bodies, must be to the vanguard of fairness for all classes of citizens and its fruits must get transferred to one and all.

World commission on the social dimension of globalization established by the ILO advocates for - *A fair globalization: Creating opportunities for all*. We as humans build enterprises and policies, but it's the human resources which are more important than physical resources and fairness in our efforts shows the ability to sustain the future for all on ethical and moral values to transform generations and regions.

One also needs to look at historic approaches of ILO, Like *ILO Declaration of Philadelphia, 1944*, i.e. Declaration concerning the aims and purposes of the International Labour Organisation, some of them may be listed as :

- (a) *Labour is not a commodity;*
- (b) *Freedom of expression and of association is essential to sustained progress;*
- (c) *Poverty anywhere constitutes a danger to prosperity everywhere;*
- (d) *The war against want requires to be carried on with unrelenting vigour within each nation, and by continuous and concerted international effort in which the representatives of workers and employers, enjoying equal status with those of governments, join with them in free discussion and democratic decision with a view to the promotion of the common welfare.*

It is the essence of workers' rights that pushes the motivation and fair work policies, ever since first industrial revolution, the industrialization has increased, so has technology, and so is the need for fair work agenda pushing decent working conditions worldwide. Global corporations should play to the local, regional and constitutional rule of the state and play their part in social responsibility.

III. ILO DECLARATION

On 18 June 1998 the International Labour Organization adopted the *ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work and its Follow-up* in Geneva, thereby decided to take on the challenges of globalization which have been the epicenter of considerable debate within the ILO since 1994. As the declaration said, “..The aim of the Declaration is to reconcile the desire to stimulate national efforts to ensure that social progress goes hand in hand with economic progress and the need to respect the

diversity of circumstances, possibilities and preferences of individual countries.”

It also added, “*Whereas economic growth is essential but not sufficient to ensure equity, social progress and the eradication of poverty, confirming the need for the ILO to promote strong social policies, justice and democratic institutions...*”

L20 has also advocated for following the principles of collective bargaining and strengthening minimum wages in order to fight growing inequality. It has also argued that the *UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights* and *OECD Due Diligence Guidance for Responsible Business Conduct* should be followed in policy action.

The International Labour Organization unanimously with consensus adopted the *ILO Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalization* on 10 June 2008. This is off course third major statement of principles, guidelines and policies adopted by the International Labour Conference ever since the ILO's Constitution of 1919. It further adds on the *Philadelphia Declaration* of 1944 and the *Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work* of 1998. The 2008 Declaration declares the contemporary vision of the ILO's mandate in the era of globalization.

It is paramount to note that the *ILO Declaration on Social Justice for a Fair Globalization* says:

Considering that the present context of globalization, characterized by the diffusion of new technologies, the flow of ideas, the exchange of goods and services, the increase in capital and financial flows, the internationalization of business and business processes and dialogue as well as the movement of persons, especially working women and men, is reshaping the world of work in profound ways:

- on the one hand, the process of economic cooperation and integration has helped a number of countries to benefit from high rates of economic growth and employment creation, to absorb many of the rural poor into the modern urban economy, to advance their developmental goals, and to foster innovation in product development and the circulation of ideas;
- on the other hand, global economic integration has caused many countries and sectors to face major challenges of income inequality, continuing high levels of unemployment and poverty, vulnerability of economies to external shocks, and the growth of both unprotected work and the informal economy, which impact on the employment relationship and the protections it can offer;

Recognizing that achieving an improved and fair outcome for all has become even more necessary in these circumstances to meet the universal aspiration for social justice, to reach full employment, to ensure the sustainability of open societies and the global economy, to achieve social cohesion and to combat poverty and rising inequalities.

The process of globalization must be positive to all, and each section of society must benefit. Sound national policies must supplement the policies followed by world institutions advocating for more frictionless trade. Local

markets, local and rural supply chains, agricultural and less skilled workforce and specialized indigenous products must be protected, so that they may sustain the tide and maintain their good presence in their own habitat.

The declaration establishes four equally important strategic objectives of the ILO, through which the Decent Work Agenda is expressed, namely:

1. Promoting employment by creating a sustainable institutional and economic environment.
2. Developing and enhancing measures of social protection – social security and labour protection – which are sustainable and adapted to national circumstances.
3. Promoting social dialogue and tripartism.
4. Respecting, promoting and realizing the fundamental principles and rights at work, which are of particular significance, as both rights and enabling conditions that are necessary for the full realization of all of the strategic objectives.

Fair globalization means better workers rights, ethical supply chain management, regulation against exploitation and remedies for disputes. Globalization as a tool to push macro economic agenda of a particular government, shall work to the good of all, if it is distributing benefits to all. Economic growth must supplement positive and progressive social transformation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The call for a fair globalization is a call for all, the fruits and benefits of international trade should be to the benefit of every one. Fairness in our approach should be to make sure that those left behind in the process, can climb up the ladder. Each worker, each job and each market place is important, our policies should solve the problem, and our policies should be holistic, in national interest and for the bottom of the pyramid. Hence Fair Globalization enhances growth and opportunities for the majority of our workforce.

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